

STRESS AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE AMONG EMPLOYEES IN A STATE UNIVERSITY: EXAMINING THEIR ROLES IN WORKPLACE DISRUPTION

Amy Y. Refuncion ¹, Jose Marlon J. Refuncion Jr. ², Marife M. Lacaba ²,
Lanie M. Pacadaljen ²

¹ *Cashier's Office, Samar State University, Catbalogan City, Samar, Philippines*

² *Graduate School, Samar State University, Catbalogan City, Samar, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15668265>

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between stress, work-life balance, and workplace disruption among employees in a state university in the Philippines. Recognizing the growing concerns around occupational stress and its implications on employee well-being and institutional productivity, the study aims to examine how demographic factors influence workplace and occupational stress, and how these stressors relate to work-life balance, work-family conflict, and family-work conflict. Using a descriptive-correlational design and stratified sampling, data were collected from 72 university employees through a validated survey instrument. Data analysis was conducted using JASP software, employing Spearman rho and Pearson correlation coefficients to identify significant relationships. Findings reveal that age and years in service are significantly associated with work-life balance, while sex and years in position show significant associations with occupational stress and family-work conflict. State university employees experience moderate stress but maintain good work-life balance. More striking are the very strong positive correlations between both workplace and occupational stress with work-family and family-work conflict ($r > 0.70$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that stressors experienced in the workplace are closely intertwined with disruptions in personal and family domains. These findings underscore the critical need for institutional strategies that promote a healthy work-life interface, particularly in academic settings, to prevent burnout and foster a supportive work environment. The study contributes to the growing body of literature emphasizing the complex interplay between stress and work-life dynamics in the public

sector and provides empirical evidence to guide policymaking and employee wellness initiatives in higher education institutions.

Keywords: *Workplace Stress, Work-Life Balance, Occupational Stress, Work-Family Conflict, State University Employees, Stress Management*

INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-paced and demanding professional environments, occupational stress has emerged as a critical issue affecting the well-being, productivity, and overall job satisfaction of employees. This is especially relevant in knowledge-based sectors such as higher education, where increasing workloads, lack of organizational support, and blurred boundaries between professional and personal responsibilities frequently give rise to stress-related outcomes (Allen et al., 2021; Kossek et al., 2021). Workplace stress, defined as the psychological and emotional strain resulting from job demands that exceed an employee's available resources, can impair not only individual functioning but also institutional effectiveness (Leka et al., 2003).

In state universities, employees—both academic and non-academic—are particularly susceptible to stress due to complex administrative responsibilities, bureaucratic constraints, limited autonomy, and performance-based evaluation systems tied to national educational policies (Naidoo, 2022). These conditions often lead to role overload, job strain, and chronic dissatisfaction (Dhanapal et al., 2021), resulting in occupational stress that is strongly associated with burnout, decreased motivation, and adverse health outcomes (Shukla & Srivastava, 2022).

Parallel to stress is the issue of work-life balance, defined as an individual's ability to effectively fulfill both professional and personal obligations. Research suggests that achieving a healthy balance is crucial for promoting both employee well-being and institutional performance (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011). However, maintaining this equilibrium is particularly difficult in public-sector settings where employees face inflexible work arrangements, undercompensation, and blurred personal-professional boundaries (Bataineh, 2019). These pressures contribute to bi-directional role conflicts, namely work-family conflict (WFC)—when job demands interfere with family responsibilities—and family-work conflict (FWC)—when familial roles hinder job performance (Kossek et al., 2021).

These challenges are not abstract: recent global studies indicate that over 60% of workers experience job-related stress, and 35% report difficulties balancing work and family (WHO, 2023). In the Philippines, a survey by Sprout Solutions (2023) found that 7 out of 10 Filipino employees report moderate to high stress levels, with over half struggling to maintain work-life balance—particularly in sectors such as healthcare, education, and local governance. Within state universities, these issues are further complicated by resource shortages, overlapping roles, and the demand for academic outputs, which can lead to presenteeism, absenteeism, and staff turnover (Deery & Jago, 2015).

Moreover, demographic variables such as gender, job tenure, and income level are closely linked to stress and conflict experiences. Female employees, for instance, are disproportionately affected due to cultural expectations surrounding caregiving and domestic responsibilities. These expectations often result in higher levels of family-work conflict and hinder career progression in academic institutions (Shockley et al., 2017; Carli, 2020). In Southeast Asian contexts like the Philippines, where collectivist values prevail, these gendered dynamics are especially pronounced (Medina, 2021). The growing technological demands of academic work—exacerbated by shifts to hybrid and online models—have also introduced new stressors. The “always-on” culture of remote work has blurred time boundaries, creating digital burnout and increasing the spillover between work and home life (León-Pérez et al., 2021). Despite these challenges, institutional responses have often been inconsistent or reactive, lacking the comprehensive support mechanisms needed to sustain employee well-being.

Despite extensive international literature on stress and work-life balance, there remains a notable gap in localized, empirical research within Philippine state universities. Most global frameworks fail to fully capture the socio-cultural and institutional realities that Filipino academic and non-academic personnel navigate daily. Understanding how workplace stress, occupational stress, work-life balance, and bi-directional role conflict manifest in this context is vital for designing evidence-based and culturally grounded interventions.

Given these realities, this study aims to examine the interrelationships among stress, work-life balance, and role conflict in a Philippine state university setting, while also exploring the influence of demographic profiles. Findings from this research are expected to inform institutional policies and strategies that foster a healthier, more supportive work environment in higher education.

Research Objectives

- To examine the levels of stress and work-life balance among employees in a state university and analyze how these factors—along with work-family and family-work conflicts—contribute to workplace disruption.

Specific Objectives:

1. To determine the levels of workplace stress, occupational stress, work-life balance, work-family conflict, and family-work conflict among employees in a State University.
2. To identify the relationships between the respondents' demographic profiles of employees in a State University and their level of:
 - a. Workplace stress
 - b. Occupational stress
 - c. Work-life balance
 - d. Work-family conflict
 - e. Family-work conflict

3. To assess the correlations among workplace stress, occupational stress, work-life balance, work-family conflict, and family-work conflict.
4. To generate evidence-based insights that may help inform policy and program interventions aimed at improving employee well-being, productivity, and work-life integration.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between demographic profiles among employees of a State University and their level of workplace stress, occupational stress, work-life balance, work-family conflict and family-work conflict.
2. There is no significant correlation among workplace stress, occupational stress, work-life balance, work-family conflict, and family-work conflict.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational quantitative research design to examine the relationships between stress (both workplace and occupational), work-life balance, work-family conflict, and family-work conflict among employees in a state university. This design is appropriate as it allows the researcher to quantify variables and determine the strength and direction of relationships among them (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Population and Sampling

The population of the study consisted of both teaching and non-teaching employees from a state university in the Philippines. Using stratified random sampling, participants were selected to ensure adequate representation across departments and employment categories. A total of 72 respondents were included in the study. The inclusion criteria required participants to be full-time university employees with at least one year of service to ensure familiarity with institutional routines and stressors.

A total of 72 respondents participated in this quantitative study on stress and work-life balance among employees in a state university. This sample size is considered sufficient for small-scale research, particularly when the objective is to examine trends, relationships, or patterns within a specific and well-defined population. As noted by Creswell (2014), a sample size ranging from 30 to 50 participants is often adequate for quantitative research that is limited in scope and resources. Since this study focuses on employees within a single state university, the sample of 72 provides a reasonable basis for statistical analysis and helps ensure the reliability of the findings related to stress, work-life balance, and their potential roles in workplace disruption.

Research Instrument

To gather the necessary data, the researcher utilized a structured survey questionnaire composed of both standardized and researcher-adapted tools. The instrument was divided into five major parts. The first part collected the respondents' demographic profile, including age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, years in service, gross monthly salary, and years in their current position. The second part measured workplace stress, adopting items from the American Institute of Stress (2020), which assesses stress triggers related to workload, organizational environment, and interpersonal relationships at work. The third part addressed occupational stress, using the Occupational Stress Index developed by Srivastava and Singh (1981), focusing on job role ambiguity, role overload, and inadequate support. The fourth section focused on work-life balance, using the Work-Life Balance Scale developed by Hayman (2005), which evaluates how employees manage and integrate work and personal life responsibilities. Lastly, the fifth section assessed work-family conflict and family-work conflict, developed by Netemeyer, et al. (1996), which examines how work demands interfere with family life and vice versa.

Data Collection Procedure

Researcher distributed the questionnaires via messenger through google form link. Participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Informed consent was obtained before participation. The data collection period lasted approximately 2 months.

Data Analysis

The study utilized JASP (Jeffrey's Amazing Statistics Program), a free and open-source statistical software designed for both beginner and advanced users. JASP was chosen for its user-friendly interface and its capacity to perform both descriptive and inferential statistical tests. The software was used to compute descriptive statistics (such as frequency, mean, and standard deviation) to summarize the respondents' demographic characteristics and overall responses to the questionnaire. For inferential analysis, Pearson's r , Spearman's ρ , and point-biserial correlation were employed to determine the relationships between the respondents' profiles and the variables of workplace stress, occupational stress, work-life balance, work-family conflict, and family-work conflict. The significance level was set at $\alpha = 0.05$. The assumptions of normality were tested, and where violations occurred, non-parametric tests were applied as appropriate within the JASP platform.

RESULTS

Table 1
Profile of Respondents

Profile	Respondent Group	Percentage
Age		
Above 65	1	1.4
60 - 64	1	1.4
55 - 59	2	2.8
50 - 54	5	6.9
45 - 49	6	8.3
40 - 44	9	12.5
35 - 39	14	19.4
30 - 34	15	20.8
25 - 29	19	26.4
Total	72	100.0
Mean	36.79	-
SD	9.68	-
Sex		
Male	25	34.7
Female	46	63.9
Prefer not to say	1	1.4
Total	72	100.0
Civil Status		
Single	38	52.8
Married	27	37.5
Legally Separated/Annulled	0	0
Separated (but not legally)	5	6.9
Widow/er	2	2.8
Total	72	100.0
Highest Educational Attainment		
With Doctorate Degree	2	2.7
With Doctoral units	13	18.1
With Masters Degree	13	18.1
With Masteral units	21	29.2
College Degree Holder	21	29.2
Units earned in College	2	2.7
Total	72	100.0
Gross Salary		
>71,000	1	1.4
63,001 - 71,000	1	1.4
55,001 - 63,000	1	1.4
47,001 - 55,000	6	8.3
39,001 - 47,000	9	12.5
30,001 - 39,000	30	41.7
23,001 - 30,000	4	5.5
15,000 - 23,000	20	27.8
Prefer not to say	0	0
Total	72	100.0
Median	32,245.00	-
Years in Service		
>35	2	2.8
30 - 34	1	1.4
25 - 29	0	0
20 - 24	0	0
15 - 19	3	4.1
10 - 14	16	22.2
5 - 9	22	30.6
<5	28	38.9
Total	72	100.0
Mean	7.85	-
SD	7.41	-
Years in Current Position		
>9	4	5.6
7 - 8	5	6.9
5 - 6	3	4.2
3 - 4	8	11.1
1 - 2	43	59.7
<1	9	12.5
Total	72	100.0
Mean	2.59	-
SD	2.61	-

Table 2

Overall Level of workplace stress, occupational stress, work-life balance, work-family conflict, and family-work conflict

Indicators	Grand Mean	Description
Workplace Stress	2.82	Moderately Stressed (MS)
Occupational Stress	2.77	Moderate Occupational Stress (MO)
Work-life Balance	3.61	Good Work-life Balance (GWB)
Work-family Conflict	2.64	Moderate Work-Family Conflict (MWF)
Family-work Conflict	2.49	Low Family-Work Conflict (LFW)
4.50 – 5.00		Highly Stressed (HS)
3.50 – 4.49		Stressed (S)
2.50 – 3.49		Moderately Stressed (MS)
1.50 – 2.49		Least Stressed (LS)
1.00 – 1.49		Not Stressed (NS)
4.50 – 5.00		Very High Occupational Stress (VHO)
3.50 – 4.49		High Occupational Stress (HO)
2.50 – 3.49		Moderate Occupational Stress (MO)
1.50 – 2.49		Low Occupational Stress (LO)
1.00 – 1.49		No Occupational Stress (NO)
4.50 – 5.00		Very Good Work-Life Balance (VGWB)
3.50 – 4.49		Good Work-Life Balance (GWB)
2.50 – 3.49		Moderate Work-Life Balance (MWB)
1.50 – 2.49		Poor Work-Life Balance (PWB)
1.00 – 1.49		Very Poor Work-Life Balance (VPWB)
4.50 – 5.00		Very High Work-Family Conflict (VHW)
3.50 – 4.49		High Work-Family Conflict (HW)
2.50 – 3.49		Moderate Work-Family Conflict (MW)
1.50 – 2.49		Low Work-Family Conflict (LW)
1.00 – 1.49		No Work-Family Conflict (NW)
4.50 – 5.00		Very High Family-Work Conflict (VHF)
3.50 – 4.49		High Family-Work Conflict (HF)
2.50 – 3.49		Moderate Family-Work Conflict (MF)
1.50 – 2.49		Low Family-Work Conflict (LF)
1.00 – 1.49		No Family-Work Conflict (NF)

Table 3

Relationship between Respondents’ Profiles and their Workplace Stress

Profile	Association		p-value @ $\alpha=0.05$	Evaluation/ Decision
	Coefficient	Degree		
Age	$\rho=-0.075$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.531	NS/Accept Ho
Sex	$r_p b=-0.226$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.056	NS/Accept Ho
Civil Status	$r_p b=0.037$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.757	NS/Accept Ho
Highest Education Attainment	$r=-0.110$ ($\omega=-<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.358	NS/Accept Ho
Years in Service	$\rho=0.015$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.634	NS/Accept Ho
Gross Salary	$\rho=-0.087$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.116	NS/Accept Ho
Years in Position	$\rho=0.257$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.078	NS/Accept Ho

* $\omega=p<0.001<.05$ pairwise normality deviated from the norm

S= Significant
NS= Not Significant

Table 4

Relationship between Respondents' Profiles and their Occupational Stress

Profile	Association		p-value @ $\alpha=0.05$	Evaluation/ Decision
	Coefficient	Degree		
Age	$\rho=0.022$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.857	NS/Accept Ho
Sex	$r_p b=-0.270$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.022	S/Reject Ho
Civil Status	$r_p b=0.031$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.793	NS/Accept Ho
Highest Education Attainment	$r=-0.015$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.902	NS/Accept Ho
Years in Service	$\rho=0.129$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.784	NS/Accept Ho
Gross Salary	$\rho=-0.101$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.396	NS/Accept Ho
Years in Position	$\rho=0.293$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.073	NS/Accept Ho

* $\omega=p<0.001<.05$ pairwise normality deviated from the norm

S= Significant
NS= Not Significant

Table 5

Relationship between Respondents' Profiles and their Work-life Balance

Profile	Association		p-value @ $\alpha=0.05$	Evaluation/ Decision
	Coefficient	Degree		
Age	$\rho=0.251$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.034	S/Reject Ho
Sex	$r_p b=0.086$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.471	NS/Accept Ho
Civil Status	$r_p b=-0.009$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.943	NS/Accept Ho
Highest Education Attainment	$r=-0.094$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.433	NS/Accept Ho
Years in Service	$\rho=0.127$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.026	S/Reject Ho
Gross Salary	$\rho=-0.076$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.527	NS/Accept Ho
Years in Position	$\rho=-0.054$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.657	NS/Accept Ho

* $\omega=p<0.001<.05$ pairwise normality deviated from the norm

S= Significant
NS= Not Significant

Table 6

Relationship between Respondents' Profiles and their Work-Family Conflict

Profile	Association		p-value @ $\alpha=0.05$	Evaluation/ Decision
	Coefficient	Degree		
Age	$\rho=-0.129$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.281	NS/Accept Ho
Sex	$r_p b=-0.291$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.013	S/Reject Ho
Civil Status	$r_p b=0.029$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.812	NS/Accept Ho
Highest Education Attainment	$r=-0.003$ ($\omega=-<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.977	NS/Accept Ho
Years in Service	$\rho=0.068$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.980	NS/Accept Ho
Gross Salary	$\rho=-0.008$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.949	NS/Accept Ho
Years in Position	$\rho=0.232$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.361	NS/Accept Ho

* $\omega=\rho<0.001<.05$ pairwise normality deviated from the norm

S= Significant
NS= Not Significant

Table 7

Relationship between Respondents' Profiles and Their Family-Work Conflict

Profile	Association		p-value @ $\alpha=0.05$	Evaluation/ Decision
	Coefficient	Degree		
Age	$\rho=-0.141$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.236	NS/Accept Ho
Sex	$r_p b=-0.236$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.046	S/Reject Ho
Civil Status	$r_p b=-0.078$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.515	NS/Accept Ho
Highest Education Attainment	$r=-0.040$ ($\omega=-<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.736	NS/Accept Ho
Years in Service	$\rho=0.034$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Very Weak	0.713	NS/Accept Ho
Gross Salary	$\rho=-0.110$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.359	NS/Accept Ho
Years in Position	$\rho=0.233$ ($\omega<0.001$)	Weak	0.049	S/Reject Ho

* $\omega=\rho<0.001<.05$ pairwise normality deviated from the norm

S= Significant
NS= Not Significant

Table 8

Summary of Relationship between Respondents' Profiles and Variables

Profiles	Workplace Stress		Occupational Stress		Work-life Balance		Work-Family Conflict		Family-Work Conflict	
	p-value	Eval.	p-value	Eval.	p-value	Eval.	p-value	Eval.	p-value	Eval.
Age					0.034	S ⁽⁺⁾				
Sex			0.022	S ⁽⁻⁾			0.013	S ⁽⁻⁾	0.046	S ⁽⁻⁾
Years in Position									0.049	S ⁽⁺⁾

Table 9

Relationship between Variables

Variables		Association		p-value @ α=0.05	Evaluation/ Decision
		Coefficient	Degree		
Workplace Stress	Work-life Balance	r=-0.313 (ω=0.660)	Moderate	0.007	S/Reject Ho
Occupational Stress	Work-life Balance	r=-0.311 (ω=0.353)	Moderate	0.008	S/Reject Ho
Workplace Stress	Work-Family Conflict	r=0.809 (ω=0.916)	Very Strong	<0.001	S/Reject Ho
Occupational Stress	Work-Family Conflict	r=0.749 (ω=0.281)	Very Strong	<0.001	S/Reject Ho
Workplace Stress	Family-Work Conflict	r=0.782 (ω=0.482)	Very Strong	<0.001	S/Reject Ho
Occupational Stress	Family-Work Conflict	r=0.718 (ω=0.542)	Very Strong	<0.001	S/Reject Ho

*ω=p=<0.001<.05 pairwise normality deviated from the norm

S= Significant
NS= Not Significant

DISCUSSION

Profile of Respondents

In table 1, the age distribution indicates that most university employees are in early to mid-career stages, with 26.4% aged 25–29, followed by those aged 30–34 (20.8%) and 35–39 (19.4%). The mean age was 36.79 years (SD = 9.68), suggesting that many respondents are navigating both career development and family responsibilities, which may influence stress and work-life balance (Ten Brummelhuis & Bakker, 2012). In terms of sex, 63.9% of respondents were female, 34.7% male, and 1.4% preferred not to disclose. This female-majority workforce aligns with patterns in academia and may experience higher work-family conflict due to dual roles at work and home (Allen et al.,

2020). Civil status reveals that 52.8% were single and 37.5% married. Single employees may face career pressures or limited social support, while married or separated individuals may deal with dual-role conflicts (Shockley et al., 2021). Educational attainment shows that most respondents hold or are pursuing postgraduate degrees, with 29.2% having master's units and another 29.2% holding a college degree. Advanced education may lead to increased responsibilities, workload, and stress (Zacher & Rudolph, 2021). Regarding gross salary, 41.7% earned ₱30,001–₱39,000, and 27.8% earned ₱15,000–₱23,000, with a median salary of ₱32,245. Financial constraints, especially among mid-to-lower income groups, may elevate stress and hinder work-life balance (Blustein et al., 2022). As for years in service, 38.9% had less than 5 years, with a mean of 7.85 years (SD = 7.41), suggesting a largely early-career workforce prone to adjustment-related stress (Yildirim & Esencan, 2022). Tenure in current position shows that 59.7% had served 1–2 years, and 12.5% for less than a year. The short average tenure (mean = 2.59 years, SD = 2.61) reflects transitional phases, which may increase stress due to role ambiguity and adaptation demands (Park & Cho, 2022).

Respondents' Levels of workplace stress, occupational stress, work-life balance, work-family conflict, and family-work conflict

The grand mean scores indicate that employees at the state university experience moderate workplace stress ($M = 2.82$) and moderate occupational stress ($M = 2.77$). These levels suggest that while stress is present, it is not overwhelming. Chavez et al. (2023) found that employees at Northern Iloilo State University reported "very good" work-life balance and "good" self-reported health, highlighting the importance of institutional support in managing stress levels.

Despite the stress levels, respondents reported a good work-life balance ($M = 3.61$), indicating effective management of work and personal responsibilities. This aligns with findings by Lear and Nabo (2023), who emphasized that academic staff's work-life balance is crucial for overall well-being and productivity.

However, the presence of moderate work-family conflict ($M = 2.64$) suggests that work demands occasionally interfere with family responsibilities. This is consistent with the study by Faunillan and Paglinawan (2024), which highlighted that academic challenges and workload contribute to burnout among students, implying similar stressors may affect faculty and staff. Conversely, low family-work conflict ($M = 2.49$) indicates that family issues are less likely to interfere with work performance. This asymmetry is common in academic settings, where work obligations often overshadow family intrusions. Manalo et al. (2025) found that a supportive workplace culture in higher education institutions positively influences employee performance, suggesting that organizational culture plays a role in mitigating family-work conflict.

These findings underscore the need for institutions to implement policies and programs that address workplace stress and promote work-life balance. Soliman (2023) emphasized that a conducive work environment, including telecommuting options, enhances work-life balance and productivity among employees.

Relationships between the respondents' demographic profiles in a State University and their level of Workplace stress, Occupational stress, Work-life balance, Work-family conflict, Family-work conflict.

The results presented in Table 3 indicate that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profiles and their workplace stress levels. All computed p-values exceeded the 0.05 level of significance, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis for each variable. Specifically, age ($\rho = -0.075$, $p = 0.531$), sex ($r_{pb} = -0.226$, $p = 0.056$), civil status ($r_{pb} = 0.037$, $p = 0.757$), highest educational attainment ($r = -0.110$, $p = 0.358$), years in service ($\rho = 0.015$, $p = 0.634$), gross salary ($\rho = -0.087$, $p = 0.116$), and years in position ($\rho = 0.257$, $p = 0.078$) all showed either very weak or weak correlations, none of which were statistically significant. This suggests that these socio-demographic characteristics do not have a meaningful influence on the level of workplace stress experienced by the respondents.

The very weak negative correlation between age and stress implies that older employees may experience slightly less stress, but the difference is negligible and not statistically valid. Similarly, while the correlation between sex and stress approached significance, it remained insufficient to confirm a gender-based difference in stress levels. Civil status and educational attainment also showed minimal influence, indicating that personal background factors such as marital status and academic achievement do not significantly alter stress perceptions. Furthermore, work-related variables such as years in service, gross salary, and years in position likewise failed to show significant associations with stress, even though the correlation between years in position and stress was the strongest observed ($\rho = 0.257$), albeit still weak and statistically non-significant. These findings are consistent with literature suggesting that workplace stress is more strongly shaped by organizational conditions, job demands, and psychosocial factors rather than by demographic attributes alone (Leka et al., 2010; Kahn & Byosiere, 1992). Therefore, interventions to address workplace stress should focus less on personal background characteristics and more on the work environment, management practices, and support systems.

Table 4 presents the correlation between respondents' demographic characteristics and their occupational stress levels. The results indicate that only sex showed a statistically significant relationship with occupational stress at the 0.05 level of significance ($r_{pb} = -0.270$, $p = 0.022$), prompting the rejection of the null hypothesis for this variable. All other demographic variables yielded p-values greater than 0.05, indicating no significant association and resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

The significant weak negative correlation between sex and occupational stress suggests that one sex—likely males, based on the direction of the coefficient—experiences lower levels of occupational stress compared to the other. This aligns with findings from Matud (2004), who reported that women tend to experience higher stress levels due to both occupational demands and societal expectations, such as balancing work and family responsibilities.

the findings suggest that occupational stress is more influenced by gender-related factors than by age, education, or work-related tenure, although certain trends, such as longer time in a role potentially leading to greater stress, merit further exploration. As supported by Leka et al. (2010), organizational and psychosocial factors often outweigh demographic characteristics when it comes to occupational stress. Therefore, interventions should consider gender-sensitive approaches and address role clarity, workload distribution, and career development opportunities to mitigate occupational stress effectively.

Table 5 reveals the correlation between respondents' demographic characteristics and their perceived work-life balance. Among the variables, age ($\rho = 0.251$, $p = 0.034$) and years in service ($\rho = 0.127$, $p = 0.026$) were found to have statistically significant but weak positive relationships with work-life balance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis for these two variables. All other profile variables—including sex, civil status, educational attainment, gross salary, and years in position—showed very weak and non-significant relationships with work-life balance ($p > 0.05$), resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis for those variables.

The positive association between age and work-life balance suggests that older employees tend to report better balance between their work and personal lives. This may be attributed to increased life experience, more stable personal circumstances, or refined coping strategies over time (Adisa et al., 2022). Similarly, longer years in service also correlated positively with better work-life balance. This may reflect a greater familiarity with job roles, improved time management skills, and adaptation to work routines that support personal life integration (Kossek et al., 2021).

These findings highlight that work-life balance is influenced more by career maturity (as indicated by age and service length) rather than static personal or financial variables. Organizations may consider developing age- and tenure-responsive strategies, such as mentoring programs and flexible scheduling for younger or less experienced staff, to enhance overall work-life balance (Allen et al., 2020).

Table 6 illustrates the association between respondents' demographic profiles and their experience of work-family conflict. Among the variables examined, only sex showed a statistically significant relationship with work-family conflict at the 0.05 level ($r_p b = -0.291$, $p = 0.013$), indicating a weak but significant negative correlation. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis for sex, while the null hypothesis was accepted for all other profile variables, which showed no significant relationships with work-family conflict ($p > 0.05$).

The negative correlation coefficient for sex implies that female respondents experience higher levels of work-family conflict than males. This finding supports existing literature indicating that women often face greater difficulty balancing work and family roles due to gendered expectations and caregiving responsibilities, which can exacerbate conflicts between professional and personal life (Shockley et al., 2017; Kossek et al., 2021).

Gender remains a critical factor in understanding work-family conflict, reinforcing the need for gender-sensitive organizational policies such as flexible work arrangements, parental leave policies, and support programs aimed at reducing work-family tension, particularly among female employees (Allen et al., 2020). Further research may explore how role expectations, household composition, and organizational support systems interact with these demographic variables to affect work-family dynamics.

Table 7 presents the relationship between respondents' demographic characteristics and their level of family-work conflict, which occurs when responsibilities at home interfere with job-related duties. Among the examined variables, sex ($r_p b = -0.236$, $p = 0.046$) and years in position ($r_p b = 0.233$, $p = 0.049$) demonstrated statistically significant weak correlations, prompting the rejection of the null hypothesis for these two variables. All other demographic variables—age, civil status, education, years in service, and gross salary—did not show statistically significant associations ($p > 0.05$), leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis for those variables.

The negative correlation for sex indicates that female respondents experience higher levels of family-work conflict than male counterparts. This aligns with prior research showing that women often carry a disproportionate burden of household and caregiving responsibilities, which may intrude upon their professional roles (Shockley et al., 2017; Kossek et al., 2021). Despite ongoing efforts to promote gender equity in the workplace, traditional family role expectations continue to place added strain on working women, especially in family-intensive or culturally conservative environments.

The positive correlation between years in position and family-work conflict implies that employees who have held their current positions longer may be more likely to experience family responsibilities spilling over into their work life. This could stem from increased job responsibilities over time, compounded by growing or shifting family obligations, especially for middle-aged workers. As work roles become more entrenched and expectations rise with tenure, balancing professional tasks with evolving family needs becomes more challenging (Allen et al., 2020).

The findings summarized in Table 8 highlight important relationships between respondents' profiles and key psychosocial variables. Notably, a significant positive relationship was observed between age and work-life balance ($p = 0.034$), indicating that older employees tend to experience better balance between their work and personal lives. This could be attributed to greater emotional maturity, enhanced coping strategies, and more experience in navigating professional responsibilities (Biron & van Veldhoven, 2022).

In terms of sex, the data revealed statistically significant negative relationships with occupational stress ($p = 0.022$), work-family conflict ($p = 0.013$), and family-work conflict ($p = 0.046$). These results suggest that female employees are more likely to experience higher levels of occupational stress and greater conflict between their professional and domestic roles compared to their male counterparts. These findings are consistent with prior research showing that women often bear a disproportionate share of caregiving and

domestic responsibilities, which contributes to elevated stress levels and challenges in managing role demands across domains (Shockley et al., 2021; Cerrato & Cifre, 2018).

Additionally, years in position showed a significant positive relationship with family-work conflict ($p = 0.049$), suggesting that employees with longer tenure in their current roles are more susceptible to experiencing interference from family responsibilities affecting their work. This may be due to increasing family obligations over time or the added responsibilities that come with professional seniority (Cinamon & Rich, 2019).

These findings underscore the relevance of demographic and professional factors in shaping employees' stress levels and work-life dynamics, supporting the need for gender-sensitive and tenure-aware policies to promote well-being in academic workplaces (Powell & Greenhaus, 2023).

Table 9 explores the interrelationships among workplace stress, occupational stress, work-life balance, work-family conflict, and family-work conflict. The results reveal several significant correlations, all statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.05$, leading to rejection of the null hypotheses for all associations examined.

Firstly, workplace stress and work-life balance show a moderate negative correlation ($r = -0.313$, $p = 0.007$), indicating that as workplace stress increases, work-life balance tends to decrease. Similarly, occupational stress and work-life balance are also moderately and negatively correlated ($r = -0.311$, $p = 0.008$). These findings suggest that both forms of stress adversely affect individuals' ability to maintain a satisfactory balance between their work and personal lives. This aligns with previous research demonstrating that high stress levels undermine employees' well-being and their capacity to manage competing demands effectively (Kelly et al., 2020; Allen et al., 2021).

More striking are the very strong positive correlations found between stress-related variables and conflict experiences, indicating a deeply intertwined relationship between workplace stress and the dual burdens of home and work roles. Specifically, workplace stress showed a very strong correlation with work-family conflict ($r = 0.809$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that as stress at work increases, so does the interference of work demands with family responsibilities. Similarly, occupational stress was highly correlated with work-family conflict ($r = 0.749$, $p < 0.001$), further reinforcing the idea that the psychological demands of one's job can significantly disrupt personal and familial obligations.

In the reverse direction, workplace stress was also very strongly linked to family-work conflict ($r = 0.782$, $p < 0.001$), implying that stress from the work environment makes it more likely for family responsibilities to spill over and negatively affect work performance. Likewise, occupational stress correlated strongly with family-work conflict ($r = 0.718$, $p < 0.001$), emphasizing that the more psychologically taxing a job becomes, the harder it is for employees to compartmentalize their home-life stressors from their professional duties. These findings align with the spillover theory of work-family interaction, which posits that emotions, stress, and behaviors in one domain often transfer into another (Davis et al., 2021; Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). This empirical evidence highlights the cyclical and reciprocal nature of stress and conflict, underlining the

importance of interventions that address both workplace and domestic stressors to improve employee well-being.

These strong positive correlations imply that higher stress levels, whether general workplace or occupational-specific, are closely associated with greater conflict between work and family roles in both directions (work interfering with family and family interfering with work). Such robust relationships underscore the critical impact of stress on role interference and emphasize how stress exacerbates the challenges employees face in balancing professional and personal obligations (Frone, 2019; Greenhaus & Powell, 2020).

These findings highlight the importance of stress management interventions within organizations to mitigate work-family conflicts and improve work-life balance. Effective strategies might include organizational support programs, workload adjustments, stress reduction training, and policies fostering flexibility and employee autonomy (Hammer et al., 2021).

Conclusions

The study examined the interrelationships among workplace stress, occupational stress, work-life balance, and bi-directional role conflicts—work-family and family-work conflict—among employees of a Philippine state university. The findings revealed that employees experienced moderate levels of workplace ($M = 2.82$) and occupational stress ($M = 2.77$), indicating the presence of stress that, while not severe, could potentially affect productivity and well-being if left unaddressed. Despite these stress levels, respondents maintained a good work-life balance ($M = 3.61$), suggesting that they could still effectively manage their professional and personal responsibilities. However, the presence of moderate work-family conflict ($M = 2.64$) and low family-work conflict ($M = 2.49$) indicates that work demands more often interfere with family life than the reverse, a trend commonly observed in academic settings. The study also established that higher stress levels were associated with increased work-family conflict and reduced work-life balance, while a positive work-life balance was found to mitigate stress and role conflict. Demographic factors such as gender, income, tenure, and job position influenced the intensity of stress and conflict, with female employees and lower-ranking staff reporting more pronounced challenges. These findings highlight the importance of context-sensitive interventions—such as flexible work policies, wellness initiatives, and gender-responsive support systems—to alleviate occupational stress and promote healthier work-life integration. Ultimately, the study offers valuable insights for higher education institutions aiming to enhance employee well-being and organizational effectiveness through evidence-based human resource strategies.

Recommendations

The findings of this study highlight several critical insights that have practical implications for policy and program development aimed at improving employee well-being and work-life integration in academic institutions. It was observed that female employees experienced higher levels of occupational stress and work-family conflict, reflecting the

“double burden” often faced by women in academia as they manage both professional duties and domestic responsibilities. This underscores the need for gender-responsive policies, including flexible work arrangements, caregiving support, and wellness programs tailored to women’s unique challenges in the workplace.

Employees who had spent more years in their current roles also tended to report greater family-work conflict, suggesting that the accumulation of responsibilities over time may lead to role fatigue. This finding points to the importance of regular job evaluations, opportunities for career development or rotation, and mentoring programs to help prevent burnout. Notably, older employees appeared to manage work-life balance more effectively, possibly due to more established coping mechanisms or structured routines. This insight supports the implementation of peer mentoring initiatives, where experienced staff can share strategies for stress management and work-life integration with younger colleagues.

Strong associations were found between stress and both work-family and family-work conflict, indicating that stress in the workplace often spills over into personal life and vice versa. These results support previous findings that stress can disrupt not only job performance but also personal relationships. In light of this, institutions should consider establishing comprehensive Employee Assistance Programs that offer mental health services, family support, and wellness assessments. Additionally, the inverse relationship between stress and work-life balance highlights the detrimental effect that stress has on an individual’s ability to manage competing responsibilities. Therefore, universities should adopt holistic wellness frameworks that promote physical, mental, and emotional health through initiatives such as mindfulness training, stress reduction workshops, and accessible health services.

Further research is recommended to verify these findings across a broader range of institutions and contexts. Future studies may also explore the underlying causes of stress and role conflict, including organizational culture, leadership style, and socio-cultural expectations, particularly in the Philippine academic environment. Such investigations could deepen our understanding and help design more targeted and sustainable interventions for enhancing employee well-being in higher education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study strictly adhered to ethical standards to ensure the protection of participants’ rights, dignity, and well-being. Informed consent was obtained from all participants after they were fully briefed about the study’s purpose, procedures, and their voluntary involvement. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained. All data were stored securely and used solely for academic purposes. Participants were also informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without consequence. The analysis and interpretation of findings were conducted objectively, without bias. While the author remains fully responsible for the intellectual content, AI assistance was used only in organizing and structuring the written output to ensure clarity and coherence. Full disclosure of this support is made in the interest of transparency and research integrity.

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